

Impact of Thyroid Disorders on Flow-Mediated Dilation: a Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

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Appendix

Search query

Embase:

('hypothyroidism'/exp OR 'hypothyroidism' OR 'hyperthyroidism'/exp OR 'hyperthyroidism' OR 'subclinical hyperthyroidism'/exp OR 'subclinical hyperthyroidism' OR 'subclinical hypothyroidism'/exp OR 'subclinical hypothyroidism' OR 'thyroid disease'/exp OR 'thyroid disease' OR 'thyrotoxicosis'/exp OR 'thyrotoxicosis' OR 'thyroid hormone'/exp OR 'thyroid hormone') AND ('flow-mediated dilation test'/exp OR 'flow-mediated dilation test' OR 'flow mediated dilation' OR 'flow mediated dilatation' OR 'flow-mediated vasodilation' OR 'flow-mediated vasodilatation' OR 'brachial artery flow-mediated dilation' OR 'brachial artery reactivity test' OR 'endothelium-dependent vasodilation' OR 'endothelium-dependent dilatation' OR 'vascular endothelial function test' OR 'noninvasive vascular reactivity test' OR 'FMD' OR 'endothelial dysfunction'/exp OR 'endothelial dysfunction' OR 'endothelial function' OR 'endothelial function'/exp)

PubMed:

('hypothyroidism' OR 'hyperthyroidism' OR 'subclinical hyperthyroidism' OR 'subclinical hypothyroidism' OR 'thyroid disease' OR 'thyrotoxicosis' OR 'thyroid hormone') AND ('flow-mediated dilation test' OR 'flow mediated dilation' OR 'flow mediated dilatation' OR 'flow-mediated vasodilation' OR 'flow-mediated vasodilatation' OR 'brachial artery flow-mediated dilation' OR 'brachial artery reactivity test' OR 'endothelium-dependent vasodilation' OR 'endothelium-dependent dilatation' OR 'vascular endothelial function test' OR 'noninvasive vascular reactivity test' OR 'FMD' OR 'endothelial dysfunction' OR 'endothelial function')

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Studies that reported only mean baseline and post-flow artery diameters without FMD values:

1. Clausen, P., Mersebach, H., Nielsen, B., Feldt-Rasmussen, B., & Feldt-Rasmussen, U. (2009). Hypothyroidism is associated with signs of endothelial dysfunction despite 1-year replacement therapy with levothyroxine. *Clinical Endocrinology*, 70(6), 932–937. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2265.2008.03410.x>
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Studies that presented FMD values exclusively in graphical form without reporting precise numerical means:

1. Shved, M. I., Martynyuk, L. P., Orel, M. A., Hnatko, V. V., & Yastremska, I. O. (2024). Clinical, laboratory and endothelium-modulating changes in patients with arterial hypertension comorbid with hypothyroidism. *Romanian Journal of Diabetes, Nutrition and Metabolic Diseases*, 31(1), 11–18. <https://doi.org/10.46389/rjd-2024-1379>

Supplementary Tables

Author	Year	Thyroid disease	Inclusion criteria for dysthyroid patients	Control group
Tan Q	2024	na	Subclinical hypothyroid patients with ejection fraction preserved heart failure	Euthyroids with ejection fraction preserved heart failure
Allam M M	2023	Graves' disease and toxic multinodular goitre	Patients with subclinical hyperthyroidism (under the age of 60 years)	Healthy matched controls
Gamal Y	2023	Newly discovered Graves' Disease	Children and adolescents (age range: 10–18 years) carried the diagnosis of Graves' Disease	Healthy children
Sahu M	2022	61.9% of cases had AbTPO positivity	Drug naïve children (<18 years) of subclinical hypothyroidism (TSH >5 mIU/ml, FT4, FT3 within normal limit).	Children <18 years age with normal TFT and Anti TPO ab level, with no h/o any form of thyroid disease.
Phowira J	2022	na	Subclinical hyperthyroidism patients	Euthyroids matched for sex, age, BMI, and risk factors for CVD
El Hini S H	2021	na	Naïve patients with subclinical hypothyroidism and overt hypothyroidism	Age- and sex-matched euthyroid healthy subjects
Farghaly H S	2019	Autoimmune thyroiditis	Children with a confirmed diagnosis of subclinical hypothyroidism because of autoimmune thyroiditis	Healthy children matched for age and gender
Afsar B	2016	na	Dysthyroid patients with Chronic Kidney Disease	Euthyroid patients with Chronic Kidney Disease
Cerbone M	2016	Absence of anti-thyroglobulin and anti-thyroperoxidase antibodies and normal thyroid echogenicity on ultrasound	Children with untreated and idiopathic subclinical hypothyroidism	Healthy euthyroid children, comparable for age, sex, height, and pubertal status
Duman G	2016	na	Premenopausal women between the ages of 20 and 45 years who were detected to have TSH elevation for the first time	Premenopausal women, whose thyroid function tests and thyroid autoantibodies were normal
McGowan A	2016	na	Subjects with overt and subclinical hypothyroidism	Euthyroids
Hosseini S M	2016	na	Subjects with exogenous subclinical hyperthyroidism	Healthy age- and sex-matched
Niknam N	2016	na	Subjects with subclinical hypothyroidism	Healthy age- and sex-matched
Tudoran M	2015	Hashimoto's thyroiditis	Hypothyroid women of autoimmune aetiology	Healthy, age-matched premenopausal women (between the ages of 30 and 50 years)
Assaad S N	2015	na	Patients with hyperthyroidism	Healthy euthyroid individuals

		na	Patients with primary hypothyroidism	Healthy euthyroid individuals
Xiang G	2014	Hashimoto's thyroiditis	Woman newly diagnosed subclinical hypothyroidism with Hashimoto's thyroiditis	Healthy women with euthyroid status
Cerit E T	2014	Hashimoto's thyroiditis	Newly diagnosed with overt hypothyroidism due to Hashimoto's thyroiditis	Healthy volunteers who were matched with the study group in terms of age, gender, and BMI
Bakiner O	2014	Hashimoto's thyroiditis	Newly diagnosed 18-50 woman patients with hypothyroidism	Age-sex-matched healthy group of volunteers
Deyneli O	2014	na	Non-smoking women between 18–50 years of age and without an evident disease except for newly diagnosed primary hypothyroidism	Euthyroid, non-smoking, age-matched women volunteers without an evident disease and a family history of coronary artery disease or diabetes
Kilic I D	2013	na	Subjects with subclinical hypothyroidism	Healthy
Xiang G	2012	Hashimoto's thyroiditis	Premenopausal hypothyroid woman newly diagnosed with Hashimoto's thyroiditis	Premenopausal female healthy subjects with euthyroid state, negative for both TPO-Ab and Tg-Ab, and without goiter by sonograms
Cabral M D	2011	na	Women with mild subclinical hypothyroidism with no previous history of thyroid disease	\
Atta M N	2011	Chronic autoimmune thyroiditis - post-thyroidectomy hypothyroidism - post-irradiation hypothyroidism	Group I: included 20 patients with chronic autoimmune thyroiditis (diagnosed by anti-thyroid antibodies and thyroid ultrasound) and hypothyroidism defined as Group II: included 20 patients with post-thyroidectomy hypothyroidism, Group III: included 20 patients with post-irradiation hypothyroidism	Healthy subjects of matched age and sex
El-adawy E H	2011	na	Subclinical hypothyroidism adolescents with obesity	Euthyroid adolescents with obesity
Turemen E E	2011	Autoimmune thyroiditis	Subclinical hypothyroidism due to autoimmune thyroiditis	Healthy volunteers
Xiang G	2010	Hashimoto's thyroiditis	Postmenopausal women with newly diagnosed subclinical hypothyroidism and with Hashimoto's thyroiditis	Healthy women with euthyroid state
Xiang G	2009	Hashimoto's thyroiditis	Sedentary Chinese Han women with subclinical hypothyroidism	Sedentary healthy women who were euthyroid
Adrees M	2009	Hashimoto's thyroiditis in 75% of patients	Women age 30–60 years and persistently raised TSH and normal FT4 for 6 months prior to commencement of the study.	Euthyroids on no medications
Cabral M D	2009	na	Subclinical hypothyroid patients with no previous history of thyroid disease	Euthyroids matched for body mass index, age and atherosclerotic risk factors.

Xiang G	2008	Hashimoto's thyroiditis	Postmenopausal hypothyroid womans	Female healthy subjects with euthyroid state
Yavuz D G	2008	MNG patients + levothyroxine administration	Premenopausal women with euthyroid multinodular goiter	Age-matched healthy female controls
Erbil Y	2007	Non-toxic multinodular goitre treated by total or near-total thyroidectomy	Non-toxic multinodular goitre treated by total or near-total thyroidectomy	\
Ho W J	2007	na	Pretreated hyperthyroid patients	Euthyroid age- and gender- matched
Razvi S	2007	na	Subclinical hypothyroid patients (TSH > 4 mIU/liter and FT4 levels in the normal reference range) and aged 18 – 80 yr	\
Duman S	2007	Hashimoto's thyroiditis	Premenopausal woman with newly diagnosed subclinical hypothyroidism	\
Dardano A	2006	Levothyroxine TSH suppressive therapy	Patients who underwent total thyroidectomy for thyroid cancer followed by ablative radioiodine treatment and TSH suppressive L-T4 therapy	Euthyroid subjects, matched to the patient group for sex, age, BMI, blood pressure, and lipid profile
Xiang G	2006	Hashimoto's thyroiditis	Women with hypothyroidism	Female healthy subjects with euthyroidism
Xiang G	2005	Hashimoto's thyroiditis	Premenopausa women newly diagnosed with Hashimoto's thyroiditis and were positive for both antithyroid peroxidase antibodies	Healthy women with euthyroid state
Cikim A S	2004	na	Subclinical hyperthyroid subjects	Euthyroid subjects
		na	Subclinical hypothyroid subjects	Euthyroid subjects
Papaoannou G I	2004	na	Hypothyroid patients	\
Xiang G	2004	na	Subjects with hyperthyroidism	Healthy age- and sex-matched and BMI matched
Lekakis J	1997	na	Subjects with subclinical hypothyroidism	Euthyroids

Table S1: Other characteristics of included studies

Author	Year	Exclusion criteria
Tan Q	2024	Patients with acute myocardial infarction; patients receiving amiodarone therapies; patients with thyroxine substitution therapy; patients with carcinoma; patients who did not have thyroid function testing; patients with overt hyperthyroidism, overt hypothyroidism, low-T3 syndrome, and subclinical hyperthyroidism; and patients who received thyroid surgery or antithyroid drugs.

Allam M M	2023	Pregnancy, chronic liver failure, chronic heart failure, ischemic heart disease, past history of hypertension, cerebrovascular disease, peripheral vascular disease, atrial fibrillation, receiving medications known to affect renal function or vasculature such as (contrast agents, nonsteroid anti-inflammatory drugs, antibiotics, ACE related drugs and diuretics), urinary tract infection, diabetes insipidus, diabetes mellitus, and adrenal insufficiency.
Gamal Y	2023	Children with other medical, systemic, or autoimmune. Cases with Graves' ophthalmopathy, toxic adenoma, toxic multinodular goiter, subclinical hyperthyroidism, or those who used drugs which may influence the cardiovascular parameters.
Sahu M	2022	Presence of comorbidities, such as heart disease (congenital/ acquired), cardiac arrhythmias, acute respiratory failure, or severe respiratory disease at the time of enrolment syndromic cases. Thyroid malignancies. Hypertension. Liver disease. Renal diseases and nephrotic syndrome. Primary lipid disorders and any h/o Thyroid hormone replacement.
Phowira J	2022	na
El Hini S H	2021	Patients with cardiovascular disorder, diabetes mellitus, hypothalamic–pituitary axis problem, chronic illness, organ dysfunction, and malignancy anywhere or taking medications that may influence the studied laboratory and cardiovascular parameters.
Farghaly H S	2019	Overweight, obese, and syndromic children were excluded from study in addition to children with other autoimmune diseases, malignancies, family history of increased cardiovascular risk, and those who were treated with medications affecting thyroid function.
Afsar B	2016	Acute infections.
Cerbone M	2016	Chronic diseases, chromosomal and genetic syndromes, previous or current thyroid diseases, use of drugs that may interfere with thyroid function, previous irradiation in the neck region, detection of SH at neonatal screening, and familial history of genetic lipid disorders or early CV diseases.
Duman G	2016	History of atherosclerotic disease, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, hyperlipidemia, or smoking.
McGowan A	2016	Prior history of ischemic heart disease, stroke, diabetes, head injury, epilepsy, psychiatric illness, significant visual impairment, or pregnancy, BMI of <18 or >35 kg/m ² . Subjects were also excluded if they were taking medication that was likely to influence the results, including statin therapy, antihypertensive or anti-inflammatory medication, aspirin, hormone replacement therapy or combined oral contraceptives.
Hosseini S M	2016	Hypertension, diabetes mellitus, coronary artery disease, infectious disease, known case of liver and kidney diseases, hyperlipidemia, menstrual disorder, polycystic ovary syndrome, morbid obesity (body mass index >30), current smoker of cigarette, alcohol abuser or drug abuser, anemia, and migraine.
Niknam N	2016	Patients under treatment for hypothyroidism; history of cardiac disease, kidney disease, liver disease, malignancies, or cerebral vascular disorders; hypertension (blood pressure higher than 140/90 mmHg); diabetes (fasting blood sugar [FBS] higher than 126 mg/dL); obesity (a body mass index [BMI] of over 30 kg/m ²); active smokers; and pregnant or lactating women.
Tudoran M	2015	Diabetes mellitus, moderate or severe hypertension, and cerebral, coronary, and peripheral artery disease.
Assaad S N	2015	Drug-induced thyroid dysfunction, diabetes mellitus, unstable angina, acute heart failure, acute myocardial infarction, renal failure, liver failure, pulmonary embolism, and pregnancy.
Xiang G	2014	Patients with coronary artery disease (myocardial infarction, ischemia electrocardiogram changes, and angina), cerebrovascular disease (transient ischemic attack or stroke), and peripheral vascular disease (the abolition of one or more peripheral arterial pulse and/or intermittent claudication and/or a past history of revascularization of the lower limbs).
Cerit E T	2014	Surgical or secondary hypothyroidism, history of pregnancy within the past year, aged less than 18 or over 65 years, body mass index (BMI) <18 or >30 kg/m ² , diabetes mellitus, established cardiovascular diseases, hereditary hyperlipidemia, acute/chronic infections, chronic systemic diseases, history of psychiatric disorders, and smoking.

Bakiner O	2014	Postmenopausal, smoking, or pregnant patients; patients with history of levothyroxine replacement therapy; calcium metabolism disorders or receiving any medications with potential effects on calcium metabolism including loop diuretics or thiazides; and patients with concomitant metabolic diseases, coronary artery disease, or other disorders that might alter protein or calcium metabolism including chronic renal failure, liver failure, malnutrition, or malignancy.
Deyneli O	2014	Smoke and any disease.
Kilic I D	2013	Previous history of thyroid disease and its treatment, medications that could change thyroid hormone levels including amiodarone and corticosteroids, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, high serum creatinine, known atherosclerotic disease, any rhythm other than sinus, psychiatric conditions, and previous pregnancy in the last 2 years.
Xiang G	2012	Obese [body mass index (BMI) [30 kg/m ²] subjects, smokers and those with hypertension, clinical detectable coronary artery disease, malignant neoplasms, renal or liver diseases, diabetes mellitus, familial hypercholesterolemia, or endocrinological disease other than the thyroid disorder were excluded from the study. Also, no subject was taking any drug.
Cabral M D	2011	History of alcohol use or were suffering from any cardiovascular disease or concomitant non-thyroid illnesses (e.g., obesity, diabetes mellitus, arterial hypertension, liver, or renal diseases).
Atta M N	2011	History of diabetes mellitus, hypertension, familial dyslipidemia, renal failures, any degree of glucose intolerance and known or symptomatic cardiovascular disease.
El-adawy E H	2011	Diabetes mellitus, hypertension, smoking, hepatic disease, infection, syndromic obesity, severe dyslipidemia (triglycerides > 400 mg/dl, total cholesterol > 300 mg/dl), peripheral vascular disease, goiter or known thyroid disease and the use of medication that alters blood pressure or glucose or lipid metabolism.
Turemen E E	2011	Any acute or chronic systemic disease, any malignant condition, alcoholism, tobacco use, hypertension, diabetes and who are younger than 20 years of age or older than 69 years of age.
Xiang G	2010	Obese (BMI > 30 kg/m ²) subjects, smokers, thyroid operation, and those with hypertension, clinical detectable coronary artery disease, and other diseases. No patient was taking any drugs.
Xiang G	2009	Obese subjects, (body mass index (BMI) >30 kg/m ²) smokers, and those with hypertension, clinical detectable coronary artery disease, and other diseases were excluded from the study. Also, no patient was taking any drugs
Adrees M	2009	History of ischaemic heart disease, transient ischaemic attacks, hypertension, diabetes mellitus or impaired fasting glycaemia, or if they were smokers.
Cabral M D	2009	History of alcohol use, were suffering from concomitant non-thyroid illnesses (e.g., diabetes mellitus, arterial hypertension, liver, or renal diseases) or were using drugs that could interfere with thyroid, lipoprotein or endothelial function.
Xiang G	2008	History of angina, myocardial infarction, congestive heart failure or hypertension requiring antihypertensive medication were excluded from this group. Obese (BMI > 30 kg/m ²) subjects, smokers, patients with malignant neoplasms, renal or liver disease, serous membrane chamber fluid, severe oedema, diabetes mellitus, familial hypercholesterolaemia or endocrinological disease other than hypothyroidism were also excluded, no patient was taking any drugs.
Yavuz D G	2008	Smokers; patients with systemic diseases such as hypertension, diabetes, inflammatory diseases, abnormal liver, or renal function; subjects taking medications, including vitamin supplementation; and patients with evidence of malabsorption.
Erbil Y	2007	Patients with clinically detectable coronary artery disease, malignant neoplasm, renal or liver disease, diabetes mellitus, familial hypercholesterolemia, a family history of cardiovascular disease, incidentally discovered thyroid carcinoma or endocrinological disease other than non-toxic multinodular goitre were excluded, as were postmenopausal women and those who declined to participate. No patient was taking oral contraceptives, estrogen supplements,

		diuretics, hypolipidemic drugs or blockers, or was a smoker. All patients with non-toxic multinodular goitre were otherwise in good health, all women had regular menses and none was pregnant. No patient had positive antibody titres for thyroid peroxidase antibody (TPO-Ab) or thyroglobulin antibody (Tg-Ab).
Ho W J	2007	Hypertension, diabetes mellitus, hypercholesterolemia, cardiovascular diseases and any other clinically relevant conditions taking medications other than β -blockers, decompensated heart failure, and a threat of diminished visual acuity due to hyperthyroid related ophthalmopathy.
Razvi S	2007	Thyroid disease and its treatment, medications that could cause thyroid hormone dysfunction, diabetes mellitus (by history and a fasting plasma glucose test), serum creatinine greater than 1.36 mg/dl (120 mol/liter), vascular disease (history and electrocardiogram), psychiatric conditions or their treatment (by history), and current or previous pregnancy in the last 2 yr.
Duman S	2007	Smokers, obese (BMI >30kg/m ²) subjects, and those with diabetes mellitus, hypertension, coronary artery disease, renal or hepatic failure, and familial hypercholesterolemia; any drug.
Dardano A	2006	Obese patients [body mass index 30 kg/m ²], smokers, and patients affected by diabetes mellitus, systemic hypertension, prior cardiovascular events, renal and hepatic failure, or other systemic diseases.
Xiang G	2006	Obese [body mass index > 30 kg/m ²] subjects, smokers, anti-DNA antibody-positive subjects, and those with hypertension, clinically detectable coronary artery disease, malignant neoplasms, renal or liver disease, diabetes mellitus, familial hypercholesterolemia, or endocrinological disease other than HT were excluded from the study. In addition, no patient was taking any drugs.
Xiang G	2005	Obese subjects [body mass index 30 kg/m ²], smokers, and those with hypertension, clinical detectable coronary artery disease, and other diseases.
Cikim A S	2004	Atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease or its signs, with other chronic diseases that could affect endothelial function such as diabetes and chronic renal failure, and postmenopausal women.
Papaioannou G I	2004	na
Xiang G	2004	Malignant neoplasms, renal or liver diseases, diabetes mellitus, familial hypercholesterolemia or endocrinological disease other than hyperthyroidism. No patient was taking oral contraceptives, estrogen supplements, diuretics, hypolipidemic drugs or blockers, or was a smoker.
Lekakis J	1997	na

Table S2. Exclusion criteria
na: not available.

Author	Year	Mean BMI*			Number of smokers (n/tot)		
		Overt disease	Subclinical disease	Control group	Overt disease	Subclinical disease	Control group
Tan Q	2024	\	24.99 \pm 5.01	4.82 \pm 4.12	\	19/79	121/413
Allam M M	2023	\	22.5 \pm 2.1	24.6 \pm 3.7	\	52/321	11/80
Gamal Y	2023	na	\	na	0	\	0
Sahu M	2022	\	20.39 \pm 2.51	18.81 \pm 3.13	\	0	0
Phowira J	2022	\	na for FMD group	na for FMD group	\	na for FMD group	na for FMD group
El Hini S H	2021	26.7 \pm 2	26.7 \pm 2	23.3 \pm 0.84	na	na	na
Farghaly H S	2019	\	na	na	\	0	0
Afsar B	2016	\	26.1 \pm 2.7	26.3 \pm 2.8	\	10/27	78/163

		\	25.4 ± 2.7	26.3 ± 2.8	\	28/66	78/163
Cerbone M	2016	\	na	na	\	0	0
Duman G	2016	27.3 ± 4.6	\	22.8±5.6	0	\	0
McGowan A	2016	26.4 ± 4.17	28.4 ± 3.96	28.1 ± 4.32	na	na	na
Hosseini S M	2016	\	23.42 ± 4.24	21.98 ± 2.24	\	\	\
Niknam N	2016	\	26.0 ± 2.0	25.8 ± 2.0	\	0	0
Tudoran M	2015	27.95 ± 2.61	26.24 ± 2.7	27.5 ± 6.71	0	0	0
Assaad S N	2015	na	\	na	na	\	na
		na	\	na	na	\	na
Xiang G	2014	\	23.6 ± 3.7	23.3 ± 3.9	\	0	0
Cerit E T	2014	25.9 ± 3.0	\	24.6 ± 3.4	0	\	0
Bakiner O	2014	27.0 (19.0–38.0)	\	24.1 (15.0–37.7)	0	\	0
Deyneli O	2014	23.77 ± 2.44	\	24.03 ± 2.15	0	\	0
Kilic I D	2013	\	28.6 ± 5.9	24.9 ± 6.5	\	6/32	5/29
Xiang G	2012	24.3 ± 2.6	24.1 ± 2.3	23.8 ± 2.0	0	0	0
Cabral M D	2011	\	25.89 ± 2.29	\	\	2/14	\
Atta M N	2011	25.91 ± 1.46	\	25.70 ± 1.34	na	\	na
El-adawy E H	2011	\	34 ± 6.3	32.1 ± 6.0	\	\	\
Turemen E E	2011	\	23.68 ± 1.73	23.39 ± 1.23	\	0	0
Xiang G	2010	\	24.0 ± 1.44	23.5 ± 1.8	\	0	0
Xiang G	2009	\	24.7 ± 1.5	23.2 ± 1.6	\	0	0
Adrees M	2009	\	na (FMD group)	\	\	0	\
Cabral M D	2009	\	26.8 ± 4.8	24.6 ± 3.7	\	na	na
Xiang G	2008	23.5 ± 3.1	\	22.6 ± 2.9	0	\	0
Yavuz D G	2008	\	24.6 ± 4.1	25.7 ± 3.2	\	0	0
Erbil Y	2007	28.4 ± 3.6	\	\	0	\	\
Ho W J	2007	21.98 ± 2.93	\	23.06 ± 3.28	6/45	\	1/45
Razvi S	2007	\	na	\	\	14/50	\
Duman S	2007	\	25 ± 3.7	\	\	0	\
Dardano A	2006	\	24.0 ± 2.8	24.2 ± 2.4	\	0	0
Xiang G	2006	23.3 ± 1.5	\	22.3 ± 2.7	0	\	0
Xiang G	2005	23.5 ± 1.5	24.2 ± 0.9	23.1 ± 1.1	0	0	0
Cikim A S	2004	\	27.87 ± 6.64	27.04 ± 4.95	\	na	na
		\	26.03 ± 6.21	27.04 ± 4.95	\	na	na
Papaioannou G I	2004	na	\	\	1/8	\	\
Xiang G	2004	18.12 ± 1.45	\	21.74 ± 1.85	\	\	\
Lekakis J	1997	na	na	na	2/12	3/10	4/13

Table S3. Other characteristics of the patients

*When the mean value was not available, the median value was reported; na: not available.

Author	Year	Mean SBP*			Mean DPB*		
		Overt disease	Subclinical disease	Control group	Overt disease	Subclinical disease	Control group
Tan Q	2024	\	126.54 ± 21.99	132.27 ± 24.48	\	78.71 ± 15.41	79.61 ± 16.75
Allam M M	2023	\	130 ± 13.85	117.81 ± 5.47	\	72.86 ± 8.09	73.13 ± 4.79
Gamal Y	2023	na	\	na	na	\	na
Sahu M	2022	\	104.86 ± 4.38	103.52 ± 6.02	\	67.57 ± 5.14	66.48 ± 6.73
Phowira J	2022	\	na for FMD group	na for FMD group	\	na for FMD group	na for FMD group
El Hini S H	2021	125.8 ± 8.8	124.4 ± 8.7	109.4 ± 10.6	75.8 ± 6.2	75.8 ± 4.9	67.8 ± 4.3
Farghaly H S	2019	\	105.0 ± 14.9	104.4 ± 12.2	\	67.1 ± 9.7	65.6 ± 8.5
Afsar B	2016	\	132.5 ± 6.7	133.3 ± 8.4	\	83.9 ± 4.4	84.2 ± 3.9
		\	138.6 ± 12.3	133.3 ± 8.4	\	84.4 ± 4.3	84.2 ± 3.9
Cerbone M	2016	\	101.33 ± 10.82	102.36 ± 10.79	\	64.98 ± 9.09	66.50 ± 9.98
Duman G	2016	na	\	na	na	\	na
McGowan A	2016	na	na	na	na	na	na
Hosseini S M	2016	\	\	\	\	\	\
Niknam N	2016	\	na	na	\	na	na
Tudoran M	2015	na	na	na	na	na	na
Assaad S N	2015	na	\	na	na	\	na
		na	\	na	na	\	na
Xiang G	2014	\	120.4 ± 8.0	120.7 ± 7.2	\	74.3 ± 6.9	73.8 ± 6.6
Cerit E T	2014	120 (100–135)	\	120 (95–135)	80 (60–90)	\	80 (60–85)
Bakiner O	2014	110.0 (100.0–140.0)	\	110.0 (100.0–120.0)	70.0 (60.0–100.0)	\	60.0 (50.0–80.0)
Deyneli O	2014	66 ± 5.86	\	72.8 ± 5.4	78.36 ± 5.69	\	77.4 ± 7.87
Kilic I D	2013	\	118.1 ± 16.8	116.9 ± 15.5	\	79.0 ± 10.8	74.6 ± 9
Xiang G	2012	126.2 ± 5.8	121.1 ± 6.3	119.8 ± 5.6	75.7 ± 5.5	73.2 ± 5.8	72.7 ± 6.1
Cabral M D	2011	\	na	\	\	na	\
Atta M N	2011	na	\	na	na	\	na
El-adawy E H	2011	\	116.6 ± 12	114.7 ± 13	\	71.9 ± 5.9	70.8 ± 1.2
Turemen E E	2011	\	na	na	\	na	na
Xiang G	2010	\	116.6 ± 9.61	116.3 ± 8.3	\	77.7 ± 6.34	75.8 ± 5.9
Xiang G	2009	\	na	na	\	na	na
Adrees M	2009	\	na (FMD group)	\	\	na (FMD group)	\

Cabral M D	2009	\	na	na	\	na	na
Xiang G	2008	126.1 ± 9.2	\	122.8 ± 8.8	77.2 ± 6.0	\	74.8 ± 7.4
Yavuz D G	2008	\	114 ± 13	114 ± 11	\	77 ± 9	77 ± 8
Erbil Y	2007	118.7 ± 3.2	\	\	71.4 ± 3.6	\	\
Ho W J	2007	124 ± 13	\	114 ± 15	68 ± 11	\	72 ± 9
Razvi S	2007	\	135.7 ± 22.6	\	\	80.8 ± 8.3	\
Duman S	2007	\	na	\	\	na	\
Dardano A	2006	\	114.7 ± 13.6	112.4 ± 12.5	\	73.8 ± 8.2	71.1 ± 8.8
Xiang G	2006	126.2 ± 10.7	\	120.4 ± 9.6	80.5 ± 5.9	\	75.3 ± 6.2
Xiang G	2005	122.2 ± 9.1	119.7 ± 7.7	120.3 ± 8.9	77.6 ± 7.6	75.8 ± 5.9	76.0 ± 6.4
Cikim A S	2004	\	na	na	\	na	na
		\	na	na	\	na	na
Papaoannou G I	2004	na	\	\	na	\	\
Xiang G	2004	122 ± 11	\	110 ± 12	64 ± 8	\	72 ± 10
Lekakis J	1997	na	na	na	na	na	na

Table S4. Other characteristics of the patients

*When the mean value was not available, the median value was reported; na: not available.

Author	Year	Mean LDL levels*			Patients with diabetes (n/tot)		
		Overt disease	Subclinical disease	Control group	Overt disease	Subclinical disease	Control group
Tan Q	2024	\	na	na	\	28/79	95/413
Allam M M	2023	\	na	na	\	0	0
Gamal Y	2023	72.5 ± 65.2 mg/dl	\	75.6 ± 13.3 mg/dl	0	\	0
Sahu M	2022	\	104.45 ± 29.95 mg/dl	87.12 ± 32.08 mg/dl	\	0	0
Phowira J	2022	\	na for FMD group	na for FMD group	\	na for FMD group	na for FMD group
El Hini S H	2021	153 ± 28 mg/dl	125 ± 13 mg/dl	83 ± 9 mg/dl	0	0	0
Farghaly H S	2019	\	94.36 ± 26.23 mg/dl	87.15 ± 18.45 mg/dl	\	0	0
Afsar B	2016	\	125.2 ± 13.9 mg/dl	123.9 ± 14.9 mg/dl	\	2/27	24/163
		\	124.0 ± 17.3 mg/dl	123.9 ± 14.9 mg/dl	\	35/66	24/163
Cerbone M	2016	\	94.33 ± 22.25 mg/dl	87.19 ± 19.43 mg/dl	\	0	0
Duman G	2016	123.8 ± 44.4 mg/dl	\	88.8 ± 28.3 mg/dl	0	\	0

McGowan A	2016	3.36 ± 1.22 mmol/l	2.96 ± 0.90 mmol/l	3.06 ± 0.82 mmol/l	0	0	0
Hosseini S M	2016	\	\	\	\	\	\
Niknam N	2016	\	108.6 ± 26.7 mg/dl	102.9 ± 30.1 mg/dl	\	0	0
Tudoran M	2015	na	na	na	0	0	0
Assaad S N	2015	na	\	na	na	\	na
		na	\	na	na	\	na
Xiang G	2014	\	2.93 ± 0.87 mmol/l	2.12 ± 0.36 mmol/l	\	na	na
Cerit E T	2014	151 ± 22 mg/dl	\	108 ± 25 mg/dl	0	\	0
Bakiner O	2014	113.0 (59.0–214.0) mg/dl	\	90.0 (50.8–143.0) mg/dl	0	\	0
Deyneli O	2014	139.4 ± 38.07 mg/dl	\	104.1 ± 19.35 mg/dl	0	\	0
Kilic I D	2013	\	na	na	\	na	na
Xiang G	2012	3.54 ± 0.5 mmol/l	3.01 ± 0.61 mmol/l	2.17 ± 0.54 mmol/l	0	0	0
Cabral M D	2011	\	137.92 ± 47.94 mg/dl	\	\	0	\
Atta M N	2011	173.00 ± 22.49 mg/dl	\	114.50 ± 14.64 mg/dl	0	\	0
El-adawy E H	2011	\	89.24 ± 15.9 mg/dl	93.5 ± 20.8 mg/dl	\	\	\
Turemen E E	2011	\	129.11 ± 32.40 mg/dl	98.51 ± 26.55 mg/dl	\	0	0
Xiang G	2010	\	3.39 ± 0.46 mmol/l	2.21 ± 0.35 mmol/l	\	na	na
Xiang G	2009	\	3.47 ± 0.65 mmol/l	2.38 ± 0.46 mmol/l	\	0	0
Adrees M	2009	\	na (FMD group)	\	\	0	\
Cabral M D	2009	\	148.7 ± 46.3 mg/dl	112.9 ± 33.3 mg/dl	\	0	0
Xiang G	2008	3.07 ± 0.52 mmol/l	\	2.14 ± 0.58 mmol/l	0	\	0
Yavuz D G	2008	\	na	na	\	0	0
Erbil Y	2007	217.7 ± 39.5 mg/dl	\	\	0	\	\
Ho W J	2007	na	\	na	0	\	0
Razvi S	2007	\	3.6 ± 0.8 mmol/l	\	\	0	\
Duman S	2007	\	126 ± 32 mg/dl	\	\	0	\
Dardano A	2006	\	112.0 ± 26.0 mg/dl	109.1 ± 23.9 mg/dl	\	0	0
Xiang G	2006	3.23 ± 0.57 mmol/l	\	2.29 ± 0.44 mmol/l	0	\	0
Xiang G	2005	3.49 ± 0.41 mmol/l	3.05 ± 0.44 mmol/l	2.21 ± 0.35 mmol/l	na	na	na
Cikim A S	2004	\	108.00 ± 25.08 mg/dl	107.70 ± 27.92 mg/dl	\	0	0
		\	100.28 ± 24.70 mg/dl	107.70 ± 27.92 mg/dl	\	0	0

Papaoannou G I	2004	114 ± 40 mg/dl	\	\	1/8	\	\
Xiang G	2004	1.92 ± 0.82 mmol/l	\	2.95 ± 0.74 mmol/l	\	\	\
Lekakis J	1997	253 ± 48 mg/dl	251 ± 57 mg/dl	233 ± 36 mg/dl	0/12	1/10	0

Table S5. Other characteristics of the patients

*When the mean value was not available, the median value was reported; na: not available.

Author	Year	FT3 normal range	FT4 normal range	Mean FT3 value*			Mean FT4 value*		
				Overt disease	Subclinical disease	Control group	Overt disease	Subclinical disease	Control group
Tan Q	2024	1.58–3.91 pg/mL	0.7–1.48 pg/dL	\	1.86 ±1.06	1.75 ±1.61	\	1.87 ±1.07	1.67 ±0.81
Allam M M	2023	2.2–5.2 pg/ml	0.85–1.9 ng/dl	\	4.94 ± 0.18	2.83 ± 0.63	\	1.76 ± 0.1	1.23 ± 0.23
Gamal Y	2023	3.5–5.5 pmol/L	10.0–26.0 pmol/L	16.4 ± 4.4	\	4.21 ± 2.3	37.8 ± 9.3	\	14.43 ± 2.54
Sahu M	2022	na	na	\	4.61 ± 0.88	4.28 +1.16	\	16.19 ± 2.46	15.79 ± 2.32
Phowira J	2022	3– 6.8 pmol/L	9–25 pmol/L	\	na for FMD group	na for FMD group	\	na for FMD group	na for FMD group
El Hini S H	2021	na	na	1.1 ± 0.5	2.5 ± 0.2	2.6 ± 0.2	0.47 ± 0.1	1.2 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0.2
Farghaly H S	2019	3.5–5.5 pmol/L	10.0–26.0 pmol/L	\	4.4 ± 1.1	4.6 ± 1.2	\	17.9 ± 3.12	18.9 ± 2.16
Afsar B	2016	2.3–4.2 pg/ml	0.89–1.76 ng/dl	\	2.9 (2.6–3.3)	2.9 (2.5–3.4)	\	1.5 (1.3–1.6)	1.4 (1.2–1.6)
		2.3–4.2 pg/ml	0.89–1.76 ng/dl	\	2.9 (2.4–3.9)	2.9 (2.5–3.4)	\	1.4 (1.2–1.6)	1.4 (1.2–1.6)
Cerbone M	2016	\	0.8–1.7 pg/mL	\	na	na	\	1.32 ± 0.18	1.26 ± 0.14
Duman G	2016	na	na	na	\	na	9.0 ± 3.2	\	13.7 ± 2.1
McGowan A	2016	na	9–22 pmol/L	na	na	na	8.77 ± 3.06	14.8 ± 2.19	15.72 ± 2.17
Hosseini S M	2016	76.3–220.8 ng/dl	4.5–12.6 µg/dl	\	142.12 ± 22.96	115.32 ± 13.9	\	9.92 ± 1.22	7.73 ± 0.87
Niknam N	2016	na	na	\	na	na	\	na	na
Tudoran M	2015	3.67–10.43 pmol/L	7.5–21.1 pmol/L	2.45 + 1.8	5.31 ± 1.7	8.31 ± 4.17	4.96 ± 2.3	6.52 ± 3.9	8.51 ± 3.14
Assaad S N	2015	na	na	na	\	na	na	\	na
		na	na	na	\	na	na	\	na

Xiang G	2014	3.20–9.20 pmol/l	9.10–25.60 pmol/l	\	6.03 ± 0.82	6.22 ± 0.73	\	16.43 ± 4.90	16.63 ± 4.73
Cerit E T	2014	na (pg/ml)	na (ng/dl)	2.24 ± 0.60	\	3.02 ± 0.32	0.57 (0.4–0.69)	\	1.09 (0.99–1.46)
Bakiner O	2014	na	na	na	\	na	8.2 (5.0–15.1)	\	14.5 (9.4–15.9)
Deyneli O	2014	1.8–4.6 pg/dL	0.93–1.7 ng/dL	2.07 ± 1.01	\	3.22 ± 0.75	0.70 ± 0.30	\	1.40 ± 0.20
Kilic I D	2013	na	ng/dL (0.93-1.7)	\	2.45 ± 0.59	2.58 ± 0.58	\	1.04 ± 0.41	1.09 ± 0.2
Xiang G	2012	3.20–9.20 pmol/L	9.10–25.60 pmol/L	1.74 ± 1.22	4.25 ± 1.07	6.18 ± 2.14	7.22 ± 3.21	10.85 ± 1.93	16.42 ± 4.89
Cabral M D	2011	na	0.8-1.9 ng/dl	\	na	\	\	0.97+0.13	\
Atta M N	2011	na	9.0–22.2 pmol/l.	na	\	na	7.21 ± 1.21	\	14.47 ± 2.48
El-adawy E H	2011	na (pg/ml)	na (pg/ml)	\	4.0 ± 0.9	3.1 ± 0.8	\	10.3 ± 1.8	10.0 ± 1.7
Turemen E E	2011	na	na (ng/dL)	\	na	\	\	1.20 ± 0.15	1.29 ± 0.14
Xiang G	2010	3.20–9.20 pmol/L	9.10–25.60 pmol/L	\	5.03 ± 0.67	5.69 ± 0.72	\	14.52 ± 2.22	15.33 ± 3.38
Xiang G	2009	3.20–9.20 pmol/l	9.10–25.60 pmol/l	\	5.52 ± 1.60	6.27 ± 1.63	\	13.77 ± 3.58	14.45 ± 2.78
Adrees M	2009	na	na	\	na	\	\	na (FMD group)	\
Cabral M D	2009	na	0.8-1.9 ng/dL	\	na	na	\	1.0 (0.1)	1.2 (0.3)
Xiang G	2008	na	na	2.04 ± 1.34	\	6.57 ± 2.31	7.19 ± 3.44 pmol/l	\	15.26 ± 4.71
Yavuz D G	2008	na	na	\	na	na	\	1.64 + 0.20 ng/dl	1.24 + 0.36
Erbil Y	2007	2.8 – 7.1 pmol/l	12 – 22 pmol/l	2.4 ± 0.6	\	\	8.5 + 2.5	\	\
Ho W J	2007	0.9–2.6 nmol/l	64–155 nmol/l	6.15 ± 2.90	\	1.49 ± 0.34	227.83 ± 69.26	\	90.38 ± 15.81
Razvi S	2007	5–8.5 pmol/l	9–25 pmol/l	\	4.7 ± 0.7	\	\	13.5 ± 2.1	\
Duman S	2007	1.8–4.6 ng/ml	0.93–1.7n g/ml	\	2.7 ± 0.4	\	\	1.15 ± 0.11	\
Dardano A	2006	2.1– 4.6 pg/ml	8.6–18.6 pg/ml	\	2.8 ± 0.5	3.2 ± 0.4	\	12.9 + 2.2	12.1 + 1.4
Xiang G	2006	3.20 – 9.20 pmol/l	9.10– 25.60 pmol/l	2.07 ± 1.89	\	6.85 ± 2.22	6.92 ± 3.51	\	16.58 ± 4.27
Xiang G	2005	na	na	1.49 ± 0.65 pmol/l	3.94 ± 0.81	5.65 ± 2.04	6.85 ± 1.72	10.17 ± 1.68	14.86 ± 3.11
Cikim A S	2004	0.27–4.20 ng/mL	11–22 pmol/L	\	na	na	\	17.72 ± 2.76	na

		0.27–4.20 ng/mL	11–22 pmol/L	\	na	na	\	14.05 ± 1.47	na
Papaioannou G I	2004	na	na	na	\	\	5.6 ± 1.6 mcg/dl	\	\
Xiang G	2004	3.20–9.20 pmol/l	9.10–25.60 pmol/l	23.16 ± 6.32	\	5.85 ± 2.33	42.67 ± 11.3	\	14.66 ± 3.44
Lekakis J	1997	0.5-1.75 ng/mL	5-12.8 mcg/dL	1.0 ± 0.3	1.3 ± 0.3	1.19 ± 0.12	5.2 ± 1.8	8.8 ± 2.0	8.48 ± 3.57

Table S6. Other characteristics of the patients: thyroid functional status

*When the mean value was not available, the median value was reported; na: not available.

Author	Year	Intervention	Time of follow-up	Mean LDL value*	Mean TSH value*	Mean FT3 value*	Mean FT4 value*
Tan Q	2024	\	\	\	\	\	\
Allam M M	2023	\	\	\	\	\	\
Gamal Y	2023	\	\	\	\	\	\
Sahu M	2022	\	\	\	\	\	\
Phowira J	2022	\	\	\	\	\	\
El Hini S H	2021	Subclinical hypothyroid and overt subjects consequently received the initial dose of LT4 which was 25–75 µg/kg and 1.5–1.6 µg/kg, respectively. Then, TSH and FT4 were measured every 6 weeks with adjustment of the LT4 dose.	6 months	90.2 ± 9 (subclinical disease) - 118 ± 27 (overt disease)	2.2 (1.9–2.4) (subclinical disease) - 2.1 (1.6–2.4) (overt disease)	2.6 ± 0.4 (subclinical disease) - 2.6 ± 0.2 (overt disease)	1.4 ± 0.2 (subclinical disease) - 1.2 ± 0.2 (overt disease)
Farghaly H S	2019	\	\	\	\	\	\
Afsar B	2016	\	\	\	\	\	\
Cerbone M	2016	Initial dose of 50 µg/day and then adjusted to keep both TSH and FT4 serum levels within the reference range.	2 years	83.23 ± 25.43	2.82 ± 1.31	na	1.37 ± 0.22
Duman G	2016	1.6-1.8 mcg/kg of levothyroxine.	3 months	113.5 ± 35.5	2 (0.3-4.4)	na	na
McGowan A	2016	\	\	\	\	\	\

Hosseini S M	2016	The dosage of levothyroxine was reduced at least 25% of prior dosage.	2 months	na	1.80 ± 0.99	na	na
Niknam N	2016	50 µg/die of levothyroxine for 2 months.	2 months	na	2.56 ± 0.69	na	na
Tudoran M	2015	\	\	\	\	\	\
Assaad S N	2015	\	\	\	\	\	\
		\	\	\	\	\	\
Xiang G	2014	\	\	\	\	\	\
Cerit E T	2014	Levothyroxine replacement therapy	6 months	111 ± 22	1.26 (0.49–3.6)	3.09 ± 0.37	1.19 (0.9–1.42)
Bakiner O	2014	Levothyroxine replacement therapy	3 months	101.0 (66.8–207.0)	2.2 (0.3–4.4)	na	na
Deyneli O	2014	Levothyroxine replacement therapy	6 months	101.9 ± 9.34	1.44 ± 1.05	3.29 ± 0.75	1.40 ± 0.28
Kilic I D	2013	\	\	\	\	\	\
Xiang G	2012	\	\	\	\	\	\
Cabral M D	2011	The initial levothyroxine dose was 0.75 mg/kg/day. Patients were re-evaluated every four weeks.	1 year	132.8+37.5	3.02+0.89	na	(1.54-4.0)
Atta M N	2011	\	\	\	\	\	\
El-adawy E H	2011	\	\	\	\	\	\
Turemen E E	2011	\	\	\	\	\	\
Xiang G	2010	\	\	\	\	\	\
Xiang G	2009	\	\	\	\	\	\
Adrees M	2009	Levothyroxine was prescribed as an initial dose of 50 µg/day and then increased every 3 months to achieve TSH levels within the local reference.	18 months	na (FMD group)	na (FMD group)	na	na (FMD group)
Cabral M D	2009	\	\	\	\	\	\
Xiang G	2008	\	\	\	\	\	\
Yavuz D G	2008	\	\	\	\	\	\
Erbil Y	2007	Replacement doses of thyroid	6 months	150.3 + 25.5	3.3 + 0.8	5.9 + 0.7	17.5 + 1.8

		hormone, and serum TSH measurements were performed at monthly intervals. The dose of L-thyroxine was increased gradually to maintain euthyroidism					
Ho W J	2007	Propylthiouracil or methimazole.	13 ± 11 weeks	na	2.11 ± 6.72	na	96.15 ± 31.37
Razvi S	2007	100 mcg/die of l-thyroxine	3 months	3.4 ± 0.8	0.5 (0.01–12.1)	5.3 ± 1	20.5 ± 4.8
Duman S	2007	100 mcg/die of l-thyroxine	8 months	130 ± 32	2.0 ± 1.1	3.1 ± 0.5	1.35 ± 0.32
Dardano A	2006	\	\	\	\	\	\
Xiang G	2006	\	\	\	\	\	\
Xiang G	2005	Levothyroxine therapy individually to maintain all of thyroid function near or within the respective normal ranges	6 - 8 months	2.36 ± 0.50 (overt disease) - 2.26 ± 0.39 (subclinical disease)	4.26 ± 1.77 (overt disease) - 4.81 ± 1.23 (subclinical disease)	6.17 ± 1.40 (overt disease) - 6.55 ± 1.72 (subclinical disease)	14.83 ± 4.21 (overt disease) - 15.22 ± 3.48 (subclinical disease)
Cikim A S	2004	\	\	\	\	\	\
Papaioannou G I	2004	na	7.4 ± 4.0 months	121 ± 31	2.9 ± 0.5	0.8 ± 0.1	7.0 ± 0.8
Xiang G	2004	Methimazole (30 mg/ day)	na	2.89 ± 0.76	4.47 ± 1.35	6.57 ± 2.00	17.90 ± 4.37
Lekakis J	1997	\	\	\	\	\	\

Table S7. Patient characteristics after restoration of euthyroidism

*When the mean value was not available, the median value was reported; na: not available.

Author	Year	FMD % ± SD			FMD % ± SD after restoring euthyroidism	
		Overt disease	Subclinical disease	Control group	Overt disease	Subclinical disease
Tan Q	2024	\	5.72 ± 1.69	7.42 ± 2.01	\	\
Allam M M	2023	\	7.03 ± 4.02	13.48 ± 4.57	\	\
Gamal Y	2023	5.42 ± 2.15	\	11.42 ± 2.28	\	\
Sahu M	2022	\	4.5 ± 1.34	8.93 ± 1.36	\	\
Phowira J	2022	\	2.7 ± 2.3	6.1 ± 2.3	\	\
El Hini S H	2021	7.7 ± 2.2	10.8 ± 1.4	15.9 ± 3	12.1 ± 2.3	15.8 ± 1.9
Farghaly H S	2019	\	4.60 ± 2.13	9.31 ± 2.29	\	\

Afsar B	2016	\	6.7 ± 0.8	7.1 ± 1.2	\	\
		\	6.1 ± 1.3	7.1 ± 1.2	\	\
Cerbone M	2016	\	12.64 ± 4.40	13.22 ± 3.96	\	13.90 ± 4.92
Duman G	2016	5.0 ± 1.9	\	6.8 ± 2.5	7.1 ± 2.7	\
McGowan A	2016	4.46 ± 1.68	5.92 ± 3.30	5.79 ± 3.90	\	\
Hosseini S M	2016	\	4.41 ± 1.91	12.48 ± 4.46	\	9.22 ± 2.13
Niknam N	2016	\	4.95 ± 2.02	6.5 ± 2.57	\	9.06 ± 2.85
Tudoran M	2015	2.5 ± 0.24	3.98 ± 0.48	11.11 ± 0.52	\	\
Assaad S N	2015	7.60 ± 5.5	\	12.61 ± 5.49	\	\
		8.88 ± 7.21	\	12.61 ± 5.49	\	\
Xiang G	2014	\	4.26 ± 0.40	5.73 ± 0.32	\	\
Cerit E T	2014	6.5 ± 4.9	\	13.8 ± 12.9	10.7 ± 5.3	\
Bakiner O *	2014	$5.0 + 2.0$	\	$6.5 + 2.0$	$7.5 + 3.0$	\
Deyneli O	2014	9.1 ± 3.7	\	15.8 ± 3.4	16.4 ± 4.4	\
Kilic I D	2013	\	11.5 ± 4.9	14.9 ± 4.2	\	\
Xiang G	2012	3.28 ± 0.65	3.88 ± 0.68	5.68 ± 0.51	\	\
Cabral M D	2011	\	16.81 ± 7.0	\	\	18.52 ± 7.44
Atta M N	2011	6.75 ± 1.42	\	14.28 ± 1.65	\	\
El-adawy E H	2011	\	3.4 ± 1.8	3.6 ± 2.2	\	\
Turemen E E	2011	\	11.64 ± 4.12	17.56 ± 4.49	\	\
Xiang G	2010	\	3.88 ± 0.62	5.69 ± 0.79	\	\
Xiang G	2009	\	3.87 ± 0.69	5.98 ± 0.97	\	\
Adrees M	2009	\	15.6 ± 2.8	\	\	$17.5\% \pm 1.2$
Cabral M D **	2009	\	$20.6 + 9.0$	$16.1 + 7.0$	\	\
Xiang G	2008	3.74 ± 0.68	\	5.13 ± 0.73	\	\
Yavuz D G	2008	\	$5.4 \pm 1.7\%$	11.2 ± 2.9	\	\
Erbil Y	2007	6.25 ± 2.10	\	\	12.58 ± 4.09	\
Ho W J	2007	8.94 ± 5.65 – 8.83 ± 4.61 (restoring patients)	\	3.77 ± 3.42	6.40 ± 4.27	\
Razvi S	2007	\	5.1 ± 3.3	\	\	5.9 ± 3.1
Duman S	2007	\	7.4 ± 4.2	\	\	9.2 ± 4.8
Dardano A	2006	\	8.9 ± 3.4	9.2 ± 3.1	\	\
Xiang G	2006	3.26 ± 0.67	\	4.98 ± 0.66	\	\

Xiang G	2005	3.27 ± 0.45	3.66 ± 0.40	4.64 ± 0.54	4.34 ± 0.51	4.45 ± 0.49
Cikim A S	2004	\	10.59 ± 4.60	15.92 ± 7.92	\	\
		\	10.68 ± 3.71	15.92 ± 7.92	\	\
Papaioannou GI	2004	3.4 ± 2.5	\	\	8.0 ± 4.4	\
Xiang G	2004	11.21 ± 1.62	\	4.32 ± 0.56	4.8 ± 0.93	\
Lekakis J	1997	4.0 ± 4.4	5.2 ± 6.3	9.5 ± 3.7	\	\

Table S8. FMD values

* This study reported numerical data as median (range), which we converted to mean (SD) following the method described in the Cochrane Handbook (<https://training.cochrane.org/handbook/current/chapter-06#section-6-5-2-6>).

** This study reported numerical data as median (IQR), which we converted to mean (SD) following the method described in the Cochrane Handbook (<https://training.cochrane.org/handbook/current/chapter-06#section-6-5-2-5>)

Study	Overall risk	Bias arising from the randomization process	Bias due to deviations from the intended interventions	Missing outcome data	Bias in measurement of the outcome	Bias in selection of the reported result
Cabral M D	2011	High	Low	High	Low	Low
Xiang G	2010	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Low
Razvi S	2007	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Duman S	2007	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low

Table S9. Risk of bias of randomized controlled trials

Study	Overall Risk of Bias	Bias due to confounding	Bias in classification of interventions	Bias in selection of participants into the study (or into the analysis)	Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Bias due to missing data	Bias in measurement of the outcome	Bias in selection of the reported result
Tan Q	2024	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low
Allam M M	2023	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Gamal Y	2023	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low

Sahu M	2022	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Phowira J	2022	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low
El Hini S H	2021	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Farghaly H S	2019	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Afsar B	2016	Serious	Serious	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low
Cerbone M	2016	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Duman G	2016	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
McGowan A	2016	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Hosseini S M	2016	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Niknam N	2016	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Tudoran M	2015	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Assaad S N	2015	Serious	Serious	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low
Xiang G	2014	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Cerit E T	2014	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low

Bakiner O	2014	Moderate	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Low
Deyneli O	2014	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Kilic I D	2013	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Xiang G	2012	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Atta M N	2011	Moderate	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low
El-adawy E H	2011	Moderate	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Low
Turemen E E	2011	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Xiang G	2009	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Adrees M	2009	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Low
Cabral M D	2009	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Xiang G	2008	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Yavuz D G	2008	Moderate	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low
Erbil Y	2007	Low (except for concerns about	Low (except for concerns about	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low

		uncontrolled confounding)	uncontrolled confounding)						
Ho W J	2007	Moderate	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low
Dardano A	2006	Moderate	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low
Xiang G	2006	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Xiang G	2005	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Cikim A S	2004	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low
Papaioannou G I	2004	Serious	Moderate	Low	Serious	Low	Low	Low	Low
Xiang G	2004	Moderate	Low (except for concerns about uncontrolled confounding)	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Low
Lekakis J	1997	Serious	Serious	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Low	Low

Table S10. Risk of bias of non-randomized studies

Supplementary figures

Figure S1. Mean difference in FMD between overt hypothyroid patients and euthyroid controls

Figure S2. Mean difference in FMD between subclinical hypothyroid patients and euthyroid controls

Figure S3. Mean difference in FMD between hypothyroid patients after restoring euthyroidism and before treatment (follow-up period of <6 months)

Figure S4. Mean difference in FMD between hypothyroid patients after restoring euthyroidism and before treatment (follow-up of ≥ 6 months)

Figure S5. Mean difference in FMD between overt hypothyroid patients after restoring euthyroidism and before treatment

Figure S6. Mean difference in FMD between subclinical hypothyroid patients after restoring euthyroidism and before treatment

Figure S7. Mean difference in FMD between hypothyroid patients post-treatment and euthyroid controls (follow-up period of < 6 months)

Figure S8. Mean difference in FMD between hypothyroid patients post-treatment and euthyroid controls (follow-up of ≥ 6 months)

Figure S9. Mean difference in FMD between overt hypothyroid patients post-treatment and euthyroid controls

Figure S10. Mean difference in FMD between subclinical hypothyroid patients post-treatment and euthyroid controls

Figure S11. Mean difference in FMD between hypothyroid patients and euthyroid controls – sensitivity analysis (studies with a low risk of bias)

Figure S12. Mean difference in FMD between hypothyroid patients after restoring euthyroidism and before treatment – sensitivity analysis (studies with a low risk of bias)

Figure S13. Mean difference in FMD between overt hypothyroid patients post-treatment and euthyroid controls – sensitivity analysis (studies with a low risk of bias)

Figure S14. Mean difference in FMD between hypothyroid patients after restoring euthyroidism and before treatment – sensitivity analysis (RCTs)

Figure S15. Mean difference in FMD between overt hyperthyroid patients and euthyroid controls

Figure S16. Mean difference in FMD between subclinical hyperthyroid patients and euthyroid controls

Figure S17. Mean difference in FMD between hyperthyroid patients after restoring euthyroidism and before treatment (follow-up period of <6 months)

Figure S18. Mean difference in FMD between overt hyperthyroid patients after restoring euthyroidism and before treatment

Figure S19. Mean difference in FMD between subclinical hyperthyroid patients after restoring euthyroidism and before treatment

Figure S20. Mean difference in FMD between hyperthyroid patients post-treatment and euthyroid controls (follow-up period of <6 months)

Figure S21. Mean difference in FMD between overt hyperthyroid patients post-treatment and euthyroid controls

Figure S22. Mean difference in FMD between subclinical hyperthyroid patients post-treatment and euthyroid controls

Figure S23. Mean difference in FMD between hyperthyroid patients and euthyroid controls – sensitivity analysis (studies with a low risk of bias)

Figure S24. Mean difference in FMD between hyperthyroid patients after restoring euthyroidism and before treatment – sensitivity analysis (studies with a low risk of bias)

Figure S25. Mean difference in FMD between overt hyperthyroid patients post-treatment and euthyroid controls – sensitivity analysis (studies with a low risk of bias)